

***Operando* laser scattering: probing the evolution of local *pH* changes on complex electrode architectures**

Vitali Grozovski^{1,=}, Pavel Moreno-García^{1,=,z}, Elea Karst¹, María de Jesús Gálvez-Vázquez¹, Alexander Fluegel², Sathana Kitayaporn³, Soma Vesztergom⁴, Peter Broekmann^{1,z}

¹Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, University of Bern, Freiestrasse 3, Bern 3012, Switzerland

²BASF SE, Global Business Unit Electronic Materials, Ludwigshafen 67056, Germany

³BASF Corporation, Global Business Unit Electronic Materials, Hillsboro, Oregon 97124, United States

⁴Department of Physical Chemistry, Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, 1117, Hungary

^zpavel.moreno@dcb.unibe.ch, peter.broekmann@dcb.unibe.ch

⁼equal contribution

Understanding proton dynamics in the diffusion layers generated by metal electrodeposition processes is of prime importance from the point of view of knowledge-driven technology development. Here we introduce a simple, non-invasive *pH*-sensing approach that is based on the Tyndall effect enhancement modulated by *pH*-controlled agglomeration events. We employ a laser beam laterally aligned to an electrode surface where cobalt deposition and hydrogen evolution take place simultaneously. This configuration allows the visualization of *pH* changes that result in precipitate formation and that extend to greater distances over patterned surfaces compared to flat ones, demonstrating a *pH*-guiding effect in superconformal metal deposition. The method provides real-time visualization of the *pH* dynamics with high lateral spatial resolution (50 μm) without physically or chemically influencing the investigated system. We suggest that applicability of the method can be extended to other processes where nanoaggregation/decomplexation inherently occur, as part of the investigated phenomena, at light-addressable interfaces.

Introduction

Numerous redox reactions relevant to medical(1), biological(2), electrodeposition(3, 4), corrosion(5), electrocatalytic(6), mineral recovery(7) and electrocoagulation(8) processes are of proton-coupled nature(9), entailing localized *pH* changes as they proceed in aqueous media. This temporospatial variability of the proton concentration at electrified solid-liquid interfaces strongly influences and often dictates the kinetics of such processes as well as the near interface electrolyte speciation. Thus, knowledge of the proton diffusion dynamics in operating electrochemical setups under specific reaction conditions and in different aqueous environments allows to improve the understanding of the reaction mechanisms and enables optimized design and control of the processes. Therefore, several experimental approaches have been developed that address different aspects of local *pH* evolution at the micro and nanoscale. The most insightful and intensively used techniques to probe interfacial *pH* are based on fluorescence microscopy(8, 10, 11), light-addressable potentiometric sensors (LAPS)(12), scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM)(10, 13), voltammetry(14), vibrational spectroscopy(4, 15, 16), electrogenerated chemiluminescence(17), light activated electrochemistry (LAE)(18), micromesh-capped *pH* meters(19) and rotating ring-disk

electrodes (RRDEs)(20). Another approach that enables access to the interfacial pH at molecular length scales and relies on the use of a concurrent non-faradaic pH -guided reaction was also recently reported(21). Although all these analytical approaches have individually contributed to the understanding of interfacial pH dynamics, they are often limited by their spatial resolution, sensitivity and invasive nature and are typically restricted to simplified model systems(22-24).

Herein we introduce a novel, inexpensive, rapid and non-invasive experimental strategy based on the Tyndall effect (TE) that enables long range real-time visualization of surface pH and pH -guided interfacial reactivity with high lateral spatial resolution. Named after the physicist John Tyndall, TE is a type of light scattering that takes place when visible light is passed through a colloidal solution with a particle size distribution that lies in the 400 to 750 nm range(25). This phenomenon has already been used as a visual screening method to detect microprecipitates in blends of parental drug solutions(26, 27) as well as to evaluate nanolevel aggregation and characterise colloidal catalyst and functional materials(28-31). More recently, Xiao et al.(32) added quantitative character to a TE-based colorimetry approach and demonstrated a *ca.* 1000-fold sensitivity improvement compared to common surface plasmon resonance-based techniques. In this work we bring forward this approach and demonstrate its excellent capabilities to investigate proton dynamics at electrified solid-liquid interfaces using a technologically relevant process as a test vehicle, namely superconformal Co electrodeposition (CoED) for advanced semiconductor wiring technology.

Until recently, the manufacture of microprocessor wiring had almost exclusively been based on superconformal Cu electrodeposition (CuED) processes on patterned Si wafers(33). However, the critical dimension of current microchip structures has nowadays approached the electron mean free path (MFP) of copper, introducing new challenges to the continuous scaling of interconnects for the 7 nm technology node and beyond(34-36). In this context, Co is thought to be less prone to resistance scaling effects and therefore more suitable for further downsizing device dimensions(37-39). Figure 1a shows a micrograph of a 300 mm Si wafer containing hundreds of advanced processor dies whose components are interconnected by void-free electrodeposited Co and Cu wiring. The specimen displayed by Fig. 1b reveals the intricate architecture of individual dies before metal deposition that comprise micro and nanoscale circuitry. Note that the manufacture of the novel Co interconnects by wet methods poses new technological challenges(40). Fig. 1c schematically summarizes the electrochemical components of the overall surface process occurring during superconformal Co electroplating of patterned Si wafers. Specifically, unlike CuED, CoED processes carried out from aqueous plating baths are unavoidably accompanied by the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), thereby developing pH gradients adjacent to the surface of the patterned wafers as they proceed(41-43). The reaction rate of these two components (CoED and HER) is expressed in Fig. 1c in terms of their respective position-dependent electric current densities j_{Co} and j_{HER} . The scheme illustrates the strong dependence of the effective Co deposition (j_{Co}) and the parasitic HER (j_{HER}) on the specific local topography of the substrate. Thus, bottom-up metal deposition and H_2 evolution occur preferentially on the recessed patterned features and their inhibition takes place on the non-patterned/planar surface regions. This enables the so-called superconformal CoED on high aspect ratio patterned features that is schematically shown in the inset of Fig. 1c. These differential Co deposition and H_2 evolution are achieved by the action of an inhibitor

additive that is selectively adsorbed on the planar areas and upper side walls of the patterned trenches(40, 44).

Herein, we investigate superconformal CoED on actual patterned Si wafers under *quasi* practical process conditions. Note that assessment of surface *pH* in these systems is very challenging as the employed Si wafers bear distinct recessed patterned fields along their surface and present, therefore, heterogeneous spatial reactivities for competitive proton and metal ion reduction. To enable the spatiotemporal visualization of *pH* changes and *pH*-guided reactivity across these interfaces, we exploited an intrinsic recognition event of superconformal CoED that leads to delayed complexation of an electrochemically inactive but *pH*-sensitive compound with Co^{2+} ions at a critical local *pH* value that develops as the deposition proceeds. This *pH*-controlled aggregation results in substantial enhancement of the TE read-out observed via a laser beam positioned immediately adjacent to the sample surface and recorded with an ordinary camera. Importantly, the occurrence of this *pH*-guided aggregation does not influence the electrodeposition process (see Fig. S1). Additionally, the proposed approach proves straightforward as it requires neither coupling with a microscope nor a translation stage for beam or sample positioning.

Experimental

Chemicals, plating solution and electrochemical cell.– $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (ReagentPlus, 99%) and H_3BO_3 (trace metal basis, 99.97%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. H_2SO_4 (96% Suprapure) was purchased from Merck. The solution for cobalt plating (50 mM $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.5 M H_3BO_3) was prepared from as-received chemicals and deionized water (18.2 M Ω cm, TOC 3 ppb, Millipore). The plating bath's *pH* was set by addition of H_2SO_4 and monitoring with a calibrated *pH*/conductometer (Metrohm 914, The Netherlands). The native *pH*-probe with *pK*_a 4.5 value also served as a marker for the local *pH* measurements. Due to proprietary reasons, the identities of the *pH*-probe and suppressor additive employed are not disclosed. All electrochemical measurements were performed at room temperature by a potentiostat/galvanostat system (Metrohm Autolab 302N, The Netherlands) in a three electrode configuration using a custom made glass cell (total solution volume of 200ml). A double junction Ag/AgCl_{3M} electrode (Metrohm, Switzerland) and a large surface area Pt wire (99.99% MaTeck) were used as reference and counter electrodes, respectively. The working electrodes for Co deposition were 10 nm Co-seeded patterned wafer coupons and 40 nm Co-seeded blanket wafers for selected control experiments. Both Co seed layers were deposited by CVD on top of thin TaN barrier layers (3 nm and 5nm, respectively). Note that Co was preferred over Cu as seed layer since we purposely employed materials and conditions that have been optimized for the actual state-of-the-art industrial application (use of Cu seed for the front-end-of-line introduces undesired electromigration effects). The patterned areas had a feature pitch that ranged from 40 to 120 nm and an average trench depth of 100 nm. Every single patterned field had dimensions of 1 x 0.265 mm². 2D non-patterned sample regions with mirror-like finish were studied for comparison. A single wafer coupon was used for each deposition experiment to provide identical initial conditions across all experiments. The recorded electrochemical data was logged in Nova 2.1 software (Metrohm, The Netherlands).

Laser setup.– The optical probe in this study consists of two parallel 5mW green lasers (532 ± 10 nm) operated with DC power supply (RND Lab) at fixed potential and current settings (2.88

V and 0.3 A) that provided equal light intensities. The laser beams were collimated and exhibited a cross section of 2.5 mm in diameter. Accurate laser alignment and positioning adjacent to patterned stacks and non-patterned areas were achieved through a manual ProbeHead (PH120, Süss Microtek) and a differential micrometre screw (Thorlabs).

Video capture.– All images and videos presented in the main text and Supplementary Information file were recorded with a Canon 600D digital single lens reflex camera with video capabilities. A Canon lens (EF 100mm f2.8 Macro USM) was used together with a teleconverter (Tokina 1.4x Teleplus Pro 300) that provided a final aperture of f4.0 and a focal length of 224 mm in 35 mm equivalent format. The videos were recorded at fixed exposure settings 1/30s and f5.6, iso800. The frame acquisition rate was set to 30 s⁻¹. Besides the minor ambient lab illumination (fluorescent light), no additional light sources were present in the lab. No white balance or any other exposure compensation/tuning was used during filming. The camera was supported on a tripod via a lens supporting collar. The raw video data was processed using the OpenShot Video Editor on a Ubuntu 18.04 Linux workstation with further frame by frame development and cutting single images in VLC Media player software. Figure S2 shows the details of the described experimental setup.

Procedure to record TE enhancement during CoED.– Galvanostatic Co deposition was performed at $j = -1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ on the basis of the geometric wafer surface area left exposed to the electrolyte. A “cold entry” sample immersion procedure was implemented with the following step sequence: i) die immersion at open circuit potential (OCP) into the suppressor additive- and pH-probe-containing plating bath (50 mM CoSO₄ in 0.5 M H₃BO₃), ii) adjustment of laser position relative to the Si die, iii) initiation of video recording, iv) application of the constant current density for additive CoED. The positions of L1 and L2 probing beams were first adjusted using a dummy sample to avoid Co seed dissolution from the patterned wafer. Once the desired positioning and laser alignment were attained, the dummy sample was removed and replaced by the actual patterned wafer to be metalized. The time between die immersion and initiation of the galvanostatic deposition was 1 min. Comparative SEM imaging experiments prior to and after 1 min sample immersion in the Co plating bath demonstrate that the seed layer is not significantly altered by the surface exposure to the electrolyte (Figure S3). The solution was agitated throughout the deposition process using a 15 mm x 6 mm magnetic stirrer bar operating at 100 or 300 rpm to mimic solution flow at the wafer surface similar to the solution flow in a real plating tool. Two to four repetitions per plating parameter set were performed to confirm experimental reproducibility. It was observed that the aggregates diffuse into the bulk solution within few seconds after the deposition is stopped when the solution stirring is 100 rpm. At 300 rpm solution stirring, the aggregates disperse and are not anymore observable within a fraction of a second once the deposition is finished.

Reference measurements by means of a conventional pH probe.– Reference local pH measurements recorded with an invasive probe were performed with a calibrated pH micro electrode (Orion) coupled to the potentiostat/galvanostat instrument via a pX1000 module (Metrohm, The Netherlands). The pH micro probe (diam = 1 mm) was supported and moved by the differential micrometre screw for precise and fine positioning. The maximal separation between the pH micro probe and the wafer surface was determined with an optical close-up tube (Macroscope 25 8x30 Monocular, RF Inter-Science Co, NY) and did not exceed 50 μm.

These *pH* reference measurements were performed with the same set of deposition parameters applied in the TE-based approach. The probe was positioned at the closest possible position to the wafer surface (patterned and non-patterned areas). The corresponding electric current was applied and the time evolution of *pH* was recorded. The probe output (voltage and *pH*) was logged in the Nova 2.1 software along with the time and applied current/potential values. After having finished the Co deposition the wafer was inspected by SEM and optical microscopy to reveal possible shielding effects by the invasive probe. It was found that the *pH* micro probe was not sensitive enough to accurately follow the time evolution of the surface *pH* developed upon CoED. Moreover, the successful superconformal metallization of the features adjacent to the *pH* probe was not achieved owing to interference with the diffusion of electrolyte species and possible distortion of the electric field.

Results and Discussion

pH-triggered aggregation of the pH-probe.– Figures S4 and S5 present beaker-scale TE experiments in which a green laser beam (532 ± 10 nm, 5 mW, beam diam. 2.5 mm) is passed through a series of inhibitor- and *pH*-probe-containing Co plating baths (10-50 mM CoSO₄ in 0.5 M H₃BO₃) with different *pH* values ranging from 2 to 6. Control experiments carried out with plating solutions containing no *pH*-sensing compound are also shown. These results demonstrate that TE enhancement by aggregation phenomena occur when the solution *pH* surpasses the value of 4.5 only in the plating bath that contains the *pH*-sensing compound. This aggregation stems from deprotonation of the *pH*-probe compound at that critical *pH* 4.5 followed by complexation with the Co²⁺ ions present in the electrolyte, thus leading to local precipitation of cross-linked agglomerates. The presence of Co²⁺ species in those precipitates was revealed by elementary EDX analysis in combination with control beaker scale TE experiments (Figures S6 and S7).

Colorimetry approach based on TE enhancement at electrified patterned Si dies.– As above mentioned, when conducting additive-assisted metallization of the patterned wafers both CoED and HER preferentially take place on the recessed areas. Under typically applied process conditions, as the Co deposition proceeds on the recessed areas, a local *pH* gradient appears and develops at the front of the rising metal growth owing to H⁺ consumption and mass transport limitations. Fig. 2 illustrates the corresponding dynamics of the interfacial double layer. In a further stage of the process the synchronized consumption of H⁺ ions on top of the trenches (with *pH* reaching the critical value) and completion of superconformal metal filling results in *pH*-probe precipitation in front of the filled patterned areas.

In the following we show how we exploit these *pH*-driven surface agglomeration phenomena to address visualization of local proton dynamics in real time at the microscopic level over extended electrode areas with high lateral spatial resolution. Figure 3a illustrates the operating principle of the developed *operando* TE-based colorimetry approach. The galvanostatic Co plating experiments (*i.e.*, at constant *j*) were carried out on single patterned Si dies in an electrochemical glass cell with plating electrolytes (50 mM Co₂SO₄ in 0.5 M H₃BO₃) containing the inhibitor and *pH*-sensing compound. The electrolytes with initial *pH* 2.5(40) were agitated in the course of the CoED at constant frequencies by a magnetic stirrer at 100 or 300 rpm to mimic solution flow on the die surface similar to the solution flow applied in a real plating tool. A large surface area Pt wire and a double junction Ag/AgCl_{3M} electrode acted as

anode and reference electrode and the measurements were controlled by an Autolab 302N potentiostat/galvanostat Metrohm system. Two non-invasive optical probes consisting of two green laser beams operated at equal intensities, aligned in parallel and separated by 5 mm from each other were accurately positioned by a differential micrometer screw so that they passed just adjacent to the outermost sample surface during the Co electroplating experiments. The primary laser probe (L1) was passed over rows of patterned fields bearing features with varying feature pitch (40-120 nm) and 100 nm average trench depth while the secondary laser beam (L2) probed the surface of non-patterned mirror-like sample locations (Fig. 3b). A conventional camera outside the glass cell positioned in front of the sample surface as depicted in Fig. 3c was used to record the time-evolution of the TE enhancement and the associated pH dynamics.

Real-time visualization of pH dynamics and CoED process progression.— The time evolution of surface pH and agglomeration events enabled by the proposed approach are exemplarily illustrated in Figure 4. The micrograph presented in Fig. 4a shows the geometry and characteristic dimensions of the patterned domains that were monitored by the laser L1. Fig. 4b displays selected screenshots (Supplementary Video 1) recorded by the camera at progressive stages during Co deposition at 300 rpm solution stirring. Additional experiments at 100 rpm applied solution stirring are provided by Figure S8 and Supplementary Video 2 and the corresponding potential transients are shown in Figure S9. The labels on the upper left corner in each subpanel of Fig. 4b indicate the time elapsed (t) after the electrochemical process was initiated. The absence of TE enhancement on the die surface indicates that the surface pH remains lower than 4.5 during the first six seconds of electrodeposition at all sample locations. Then at $t = 7$ s light scattering events start becoming apparent only at specific sample locations adjacent to the probing laser L1 (only on patterned sample regions with feature pitch 40-50 nm that develop large local current densities). Conversely, no apparent scattering events other than background events can be observed at the interfacial sample regions probed by L2. This indicates that at this stage, precipitation of the pH -probe compound selectively takes place at those patterned sample locations because their local pH reaches the critical value due to HER as the front of the deposited Co approaches the outermost sample surface. Note that these agglomeration events remain physically confined to the parallel patterned domains that in the probed surface region are separated from each other by 50 μm spacings (see Figure S10) and that fields with larger feature pitch (85-120 nm) where the local current density is comparably lower have not yet reached the critical pH . This proves that our approach enables μm -scale spatial resolution ($< 50 \mu\text{m}$) of the local pH -guided reactivity over laterally extended macroscopic samples and that the intensity of the associated TE enhancement directly correlates with the position-dependent current density (Figures S11 and S12).

As the electrodeposition proceeds, within $8 \text{ s} \leq t \leq 15 \text{ s}$, an increasing number of patterned fields gradually achieve successful superconformal filling and the concomitant change of pH and pH -probe precipitation occurring in the locations probed by L1 can be instantly and straightforwardly followed based on the observed scattering enhancement. At $t = 16$ s the increase in pH far beyond the critical value and the accumulation of precipitated Co^{2+} - pH -probe complex become obvious from the increased TE enhancement at those locations that were firstly filled (Fig. S12). At this moment light scattering becomes observable for the first time on the non-patterned sample surface probed by the L2 beam. The reason for this delay in local pH increase and accompanying pH -probe precipitation is the presence of the inhibitor

layer adsorbed on the flat sample areas that slows down the kinetics of both the HER and CoED(40). Continuation of the galvanostatic Co deposition eventually leads to the interfacial pH surpassing the marker threshold at all sample locations, that results in the even Co deposition along the entire Si die. Specifically, at $t \geq 24$ s the increased $pH > 4.5$ on top of the flat sample locations separating recessed domains leads to losses in lateral spatial resolution. Finally, at $t \geq 35$ s massive Co^{2+} - pH -probe precipitation due to the progressive alkalisation of the diffusion layer all over the sample sets in and both L1 and L2 probes reveal increasingly similar scattering phenomena. The higher intensity of the light scattering is, nonetheless, still observable on the patterned regions. Note that the enhancement of the Tyndall effect occurs at comparably earlier stages when the magnetic stirrer placed at the bottom of the electrochemical cell is rotated at 100 rpm because the mass transport limitations for the H^+ ion are more substantial at lower stirring rates (Figure S8).

To demonstrate that the observed pH dynamics and resulting agglomeration originate from surface-confined electrochemically-driven transformations we carried out the following control investigations. First, CoED experiments performed under identical plating conditions as discussed above but placing the laser system 50 μm away from the sample surface exhibited much weaker scattering enhancement. Further, a second series of reference experiments carried out with laser irradiation adjacent to the sample surface but without pH -probe in the plating electrolyte showed no TE enhancement at all surface metallization stages. Finally, experiments with all plating components but conducted at zero total transferred charge (in the absence of electrochemical processes) equally showed no TE enhancement. The corresponding Figures S13-S15 are included in the Supplementary Information file.

Confirmation by numerical simulations.– The scenario described before can also be confirmed by finite element-based numerical simulations if we assume variables (Co^{2+} concentration, pH , applied current density j) that exactly match the applied experimental conditions, and we use physical parameter values (charge transfer and reaction rate coefficients) in the simulations that were described elsewhere for Co electrodeposition. Note that prior diffusion modelling of additive-assisted bottom-up Cu filling by Akolkar et al. have successfully explored how concentration fields (for additives, not H^+ ions) develop near patterned surfaces as well as the dependence of such fields on pattern density(45). In our simulation routine (details are explained in the Supplementary Information file), it is enough to handle two simultaneously occurring electrode processes (CoED and the HER) and to account for mass transfer processes supplying reactants. To deal with surface heterogeneities, we assumed that both electrode reactions have a 100-fold decreased activity over the (additive-blocked) planar surfaces, while the reactions run unhindered at trenced areas. Figure 5 presents the time evolution of pH profiles on the surface of a simulated Si die segment that comprises three patterned fields (black recessed rectangles). Selected screenshots of the proton dynamics at times matching those displayed in Fig. 4b are shown and those of the corresponding Co^{2+} concentration profiles can be found in Figure S16. Both pH and Co^{2+} concentration profiles show that protons and Co^{2+} ions are more rapidly consumed on the surface of the patterned fields than on flat sample areas in the course of the plating process. Note in Fig. 5 that as the electrolysis proceeds, the resulting accelerated alkalisation beyond the critical pH value at $t = 9$ s initially remains confined on top of the recessed fields and that for the following 3 s there is no overlap of individually developing mushroom-like pH profiles.

This matches the evolution of the *pH*-guided precipitation phenomena revealed by the L1 probe during the first 16 s in Fig. 4b. Despite the slight temporal mismatch between the experimental and the simulated data, their qualitative agreement with regards to *pH* dynamics and *pH*-guided agglomeration is remarkable. At more advanced process stages ($t > 12$ s in Fig. 5), attainment and subsequent surpassing of the critical *pH* value not only on recessed areas but also on top of the adjacent flat sample locations leads to the loss in lateral spatial resolution of the interfacial *pH* concomitant with the expansion of the diffusion layer. This correlates with the experimental Tyndall effect observations at $t \geq 24$ s in Fig. 4b. Complementary simulations that account for solution stirring effects are presented in Figs. S17 and S18.

Conclusions

Overall, the presented *operando* TE-based approach constitutes a significant progress in analytical strategies aiming at investigating the dynamics of the interfacial double layer because it provides instantaneous extended *pH* read-out on surfaces with distinct local reactivities and unique spatiotemporal resolution only limited by the acquisition capabilities of the employed camera (here 30 reactivity maps per second). Besides straightforwardly enabling comparative reaction kinetics intrinsic to complex electrode architectures, the approach is also amenable to quantification and might exhibit outstanding sensitivity(32). Finally, its applicability can be extended to other nanoaggregation/decomplexation process (*e.g.*, electrocoagulation, mineral removal and separation, electrosynthesis, among others) occurring at light-addressable interfaces provided the corresponding environments contain divalent cations. This work provides therefore useful means to improve the understanding of such interfacial processes and control over them.

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Figure 1. (a) A 300 mm Si wafer bearing hundreds of processor dies manufactured by lithographic and electrochemical deposition methods (CoED and CuED). (b) Magnified view of a 300 mm Si wafer before Co metallization that reveals the internal structural complexity of individual patterned dies. (c) Schematic representation of the position-dependent current density distribution along the surface of a patterned wafer during CoED. j_{Co} and j_{HER} stand for the partial current density contributions to the total current density j_{tot} from CoED and parasitic HER, respectively. The inset in (c) schematically shows cross-sectioned trenches after having been superconformally electroplated.

Figure 2. (a) and (b) Dynamics of the metal deposition and proton reduction taking place in the course of CoED on patterned wafers.

Figure 3. (a) Experimental arrangement for CoED experiments coupled to pH probing by a non-invasive tandem laser beam. (b) and (c) Front and side views of the laser probe positioning relative to the Si die during sample metallization.

Figure 4. (a) Optical micrograph of a Co-seeded Si die section scrutinized by the TE-based colorimetry approach. The characteristic feature pitch of each patterned ensemble is indicated by arrows. (b) Selected screenshots captured at different stages of the superconformal Co electrodeposition process by a camera placed in front of the Si die. The labels on the upper left corner of each subpanel indicate the time elapsed after the galvanostatic metal deposition was started. Scale bars: 1000 μm for all subpanels in (b). The plating bath contained both inhibitor additive and pH-sensitive compound and the CoED was conducted at $j = -1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ and 300 rpm. Each adjacent patterned domain probed by L1 comprises an area of 0.265 mm^2 and is separated from the closest neighbours by 50 μm .

Figure 5. Selected screenshots of pH profiles captured at different stages of the simulated Co electrodeposition process. The labels on the upper central part of each subpanel indicate the time elapsed after the galvanostatic metal deposition at $j = -1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ had been started. The initial pH of the plating bath at $t = 0$ was set to 2.5. The blocking effect of the inhibitor additive adsorbed on non-patterned sample surface regions is achieved in the calculations by setting $k_{\text{HER}}(\text{patterned})/k_{\text{HER}}(\text{flat}) = 100$, where k_{HER} stands for the reaction rate coefficient for the HER. The contour lines indicate the experimentally detectable pH 4.5.